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'To what extent can EAL provision within a boarding school be further developed to better support its stakeholders?'

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Abstract

The international school market currently comprises 14,356 schools and approximately 7.2 million students in a globally dynamic and competitive sector which generates over \$63 billion each year. Despite being an integral part of this market, boarding schools face sustainability challenges that reflect fluctuating enrollment trends and fierce competition. Nowhere is this more so than in Thailand where, with boarding and tuition fees of up to \$42,510 per year, almost constant consideration is given to the financial stakes of maintaining and growing student numbers whilst continually providing high standards of pastoral care and academic development in fee paying schools. English language proficiency is extensively identified as a critical factor for academic success and future employability and while there has been much research in respective areas of both the importance and delivery of English Language development little has been done to understand the impact that living in a school-age, residential setting has on the development of English language. To evaluate the provision of English language development in a co-ed, British International boarding school in Thailand, a combination of online questionnaires and face to face interviews were conducted with students, staff and parents. Questions aimed to explore the current provision, benefits to stakeholders and the barriers to developing provision further. Key findings from the research identify barriers including staff numbers and training, the impact of large, low ability, same nationality groups and the current day school English as an additional language curriculum as key factors that can be developed to improve current provision. Suggestions include specialist evening lessons for residential students and the potential for a separate, immersive language programme as a replacement or parallel to current day school provision. Recommendations for further research are also presented.

Chapter 1 Introduction

According to the ISC Research Teacher Movement Report (2024), the international schools market comprises 14,356 schools that cater to 7.2 million students. These institutions employ over 686,000 teachers and generate more than \$63 billion in annual tuition fees. In Asia alone, the market includes more than half of these students, totaling 4,585,416, across 8,233 schools. Thailand in particular is saturated with 163 international schools offering a variety of curriculums including American, International Baccalaureate (IB) and British (GCSE's, BTEC and A-level). Of the 163 international schools located in Thailand, 30 are boarding schools and 13 of these are in Bangkok. International Boarding school fees across Thailand range from \$18,421 to \$42,510 (International Schools Database, 2024).

With such a saturated, competitive and continually expanding market, maintaining and expanding the number of boarding students is crucial for a boarding school's financial health. It is a key factor in a school's sustainability to offer a dynamic, vibrant and relevant curriculum and programme of activities that support the full integration of international students from diverse cultural backgrounds which at the same time prepares them for life on a global stage (Li, 2024). In a study carried out by Steel *et al* (2015) it was revealed that when considering the potential for enhanced outcomes in employment, income, health, and volunteerism for school graduates is important to note that language plays a key role in the growth, integration and academic success of students, particularly in a boarding community.

Morgan (2004) conducted a survey of boarding parents and students, which surmised that boarding schools provide a unique opportunity for students to immerse themselves in their education, thrive within a diverse and supportive community, and prepare for future success. Morgans' findings suggested that boarding school students who possess strong English language skills felt better prepared for life after graduation, are more likely to pursue advanced degrees, and generally rated their school experience highly. Consequently, it is vital for boarding schools to develop and market the distinctive benefits of their educational programmes in order to recruit and retain students.

Morgans' (2004) findings were later referenced by Keyuravong (2010) in his research for the Thai Ministry of Education, on policy development and opportunities for English-proficient students. Keyuravong's study found that in many Asian countries, including Thailand, English is perceived by parents and students as a key driver of

economic progress and well-being. Improving English skills is thus seen as a significant factor in achieving future career success.

In the literature on the relationship between English proficiency and employability there is general agreement that employers and universities favour applications from those with better English skills, particularly in a global marketplace. There is less consensus over whether or not the best way to achieve this is via English lessons taught through schools or through English Language Development (ELD) programmes (of which there are many kinds including private tuition).

Hodges, Sheffield and Ralph (2013), suggests there has been a general decline in full boarding due to the increase in the number of schools offering weekly and flexi-boarding. The Independent School's Council (ISC) annual reports from 2019-2020 inclusive also voiced concern about the decline of schools that offered boarding and in particular the small number of schools (2.2%) that are exclusively boarding.

Whilst there is widespread agreement that the idea that COVID-19 and upcoming government plans to charge VAT on independent school fees are central to more recent theories regarding boarding decline in the UK, it is also important to recognise the negative press that boarding schools have received within the UK, not ignoring the previous works of; Schaverien (2011), whose work openly discusses 'boarding school syndrome', Renton (2014) whose article in the Guardian, details accounts of historical child physical and sexual abuse and also Green and Kynaston (2019) who's article in the same paper, entitled "Britain's private school problem" where they called for the closure of all independent sector schools claiming that boarding schools are not only hot-spots for abuse but potentially damage society as a whole. An attitude potentially backed by the Labour Party who are considering taxing independent school fees if they get elected later this year, a move which would force many small independent schools that offer boarding to close.

In contrast to what may be perceived as a potentially bleak outlook for UK boarding, the international boarding scene is seeing wide spread growth. Clive Pierrpont (as cited in Keeling and Brummitt, 2013. pg 29), Director of Communications at Taaleen, which owns and manages 13 international school across Dubai and Abu Dhabi, discussed the ever increasing opportunities for wealthy local families to enrol their children at an international schools, who today make up around 80% of all children at international schools, a stark contrast to 30 years ago when 80% of students on roll belonged to expatriate families. Research conducted in 2024 by ISC Research

suggests there are a total of 13,614 English-Medium international schools around the world enrolling approximately 7 million students in a sector that is generating over \$58 billion USD, and demonstrates growth of 18% in the last five years.

The current state of boarding requires schools to be both dynamic and proactive in their development in order to survive in either the UK market where boarding schools are still recovering from negative press as well as the ever expanding, highly competitive international market.

A study carried out by Varney and Collins (2022), on 'The Sustainability of Small Independent Schools' found that amongst the top concerns for school leaders was 'Sustainability challenges' and that almost all leaders identified challenges related to enrollment and financial concerns. These were related to finding new revenue sources in order to attract full-pay (non bursary) families. With this in mind and with an ever increasing number of international schools opening it is more important than ever for schools, in particular boarding schools, to take a critical look at what they offer in order to be proactive rather than reactive to the ever changing wants and needs of international students and parents (Briedienstien *et al* 2018 and White, 2004). Maintaining and growing boarding student numbers is vital for the economic situation of a boarding school and being able to deliver and maintain a vibrant curriculum and activities programme that enables international students from varying cultural backgrounds to be fully integrated into the community is key to this (Hayden and Thompsom, 2001)

Is there room for reformation and expansion of existing programmes offered by boarding schools to students that could offer potential benefits across several areas of the school ultimately impacting on recruitment, retention and academic achievement. This research looks to explore the following three areas in order to answer the research question.

1. Explore the current provision for English Language development available in School A.
2. Evaluate the benefits for stakeholders within a boarding school for developing English language programmes.
3. Determine the barriers and limitations of programme development in a residential setting.

This research reviews current literature in these areas as well as a discussion regarding researcher positionality and research methods and methodology in order to deduce which are the most appropriate methods to gain insight into the research

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questions. Findings are discussed and suggestions for future research and improved practice are made.

Chapter 2 Literature Review

The environment in which students grow and develop has the ability to directly influence academic progress and school outcomes (Crepeele, 2022) nowhere could this be considered more true than the boarding environment (Papworth, 2014). Where Crepeele's research was primarily focussed on the gap between private funded and state provided education and those who are at the bottom of the socioeconomic spectrum, Papworth's research looks in depth at the impact that living in a boarding school has on academic outcomes.

There is a plethora of research relating to various aspects of boarding although the majority of this is focussed in America and is centred on higher education (Pike, 1999 and Yao, 2014), small cultural group studies (Colmant, 2000) or the socio economic divide (Behaghel, Chaisemartin, and Gurgand, 2017). Much research into the British boarding school system is monopolised by the marred history of student experiences in boarding schools, extensively researched and reported by Schaverien (2004, 2011 and 2015), who suggest an archetypal experience of abuse and trauma or more recently the work of James (2023), who looks less at the abuse/trauma aspect but focuses on the psychological impact of sending a child to boarding school. Sadly much of the research into British boarding schools in the United Kingdom paints a bleak and unwelcoming picture and does little to promote a positive picture of boarding and all of the academic and holistic skills that it is able to develop as identified by Lawrence (2005) and later by Sillitoe (2010). This bleak picture and bias of research may well be a contributing factor as the steady decline in boarding numbers and the need for school to paint a very different picture for parents particularly as this directly impacts on students numbers and for many 'for profit' schools income.

It can be argued that the decline in boarding school places and the boom in the international school market has led to a renewed interest in several areas including; student recruitment, recruitment of boarding students and the schools outcomes for students who attend international school. As mentioned previously, research conducted in 2023 and mentioned in the 2004 report by ISC Research suggests there are a total of 13,614 English-Medium international schools around the world enrolling approximately 7 million students in a sector that is generating over \$58 billion USD, and demonstrates growth of 18% in the last five years. International school places in Thailand are highly competitive driving schools to continuously create and develop dynamic programmes that educate the 'whole child' and look at

development of other areas not solely academic success (Hayden and Thompson, 2008).

The role of the English language and its impact on academic outcomes and employability has been extensively studied. English has come to be the international language and the language of global communication, due to various reasons which are political, economical and technical. Globalisation has made English a compulsory ingredient of a successful personality as it is an important tool widely used in international communication all over the world as suggested by Rao (2016) who researches the direct correlation between English and employability. Whereas I disagree with Rao's suggestion that good English is linked to a successful personality and that it is the experience and outcomes of students that is affected by English proficiency, (Yeung, Linver, and Brooks-Gunn, 2002) identify that parents also make substantial links between personality or character development, English proficiency and financial success.

Hynes and Bhatia (1996), discuss communication skills in English have been identified as indispensable workplace tools for success in business and that communication skills in English play a significant role as technology increases the speed of efficacy of messages. Business communication studies have cited the numerous hours that people in a managerial role spend communicating with others (Krizan, Merrier and Jones, 2002), or to writing correspondence and reports (Ober, 2003), and ultimately their ability to earn higher salaries if they have strong writing skills (Fisher, 2010).

Although a considerable body of research focussed on the most effective ways to deliver English Language programmes, less attention has been paid to the influence that a residential setting may have on this. The bulk of research in the areas focuses more on the English language instruction and outcomes for students that happen to be residential rather than research with a specific focus on the impact of the residential setting.

Foss, McDonald and Rooks, (2008), noted an impact that when students were living with teachers and classmates, especially when part of an intensive course, that such an arrangement enables students to interact with speakers of the English Language in a more natural environment. It also provides cross-cultural experience for other students in the residential setting, this has further impact when the residential setting has bilingual staff, especially with students who are new to a second language. Earlier work by Tarone and Swain (1995), discuss how constructive guidelines for building an EAL programme should involve children in immersive

activities outside the classroom with peers who are native speakers of the new language, something which is easy to achieve within a boarding community. One of the most persistent problems for teachers is the tendency of older immersion students not to use L2 in the classroom, particularly when conversing with each other. This mirrored findings from the SWOT analysis (Appendix 2 and 3), that despite an English speaking policy in communal areas, students tended to speak only in L1.

It is also important to consider the local relevance of language in international schools and should include Keyuravong (2010), whose ongoing research helps to inform the Ministry of Education (MOE) in Thailand with their 'English Bilingual Education' (EBE) policy. The MOE issued the document 'Policy, Principles and Process of Teaching and Learning's Management of Ministry of Education's Curriculum in English' (Bureau of Education, Innovation Development, 2001). The policy can be briefly summarised as follows: The EBE Programme is considered an alternative education for schools (all non Thai schools would fall into this category). The EBE programme must preserve the security of the nation, religion, royalty, the Thai language, Thai art and Thai tradition and culture. The programme must be systematically supervised and assessed at regular intervals to continuously solve problems and to improve the quality of instruction. The management of the programme must follow the guidelines, procedures and regulations in the curriculum stipulated by the Ministry of Education. Similar programmes exist in many other countries with a focus on facilitation for international schools to promote English while at the same time preserving and promoting local culture.

Cultural influences will be an important consideration given that the research is focussed on a fee paying, British boarding school located in Thailand with a cohort of twelve nationalities in the boarding community alone and where 80% of the students have English as an additional language. Where early research into cultural engagement with school programmes makes few links, more recent research by Moussu (2006) and Glass, Wongtrirat and Buus (2015) identified four key areas which Asian learners value in an intensive English programme; teaching quality, characteristics of people in the institution, learning environment and expectation of oneself. She comments that engagement and learning were maximised when content was delivered with a clear context and purpose. Students needed to know the 'real-life' applications for what they were learning. Although research by Mondragon (2012) draws little to no links regarding the importance of cultural group engagement and integration in multicultural residential settings, this is in stark contrast to Martin (2013) who suggests this information is particularly valuable when

working in a diverse community such as boarding where English would be taught by both native and non-native speakers.

Given the lack of research specifically looking at the relationship between boarding, English language and international schools. This research will look to explore the current provision in one sample school and if there is potential for better English Language provision to benefit students, parents and staff. There is no existing research into British international boarding schools based in Thailand with the most comparable studies being by Sabawi (2014) in Dubai however this looks at social networks impact on boarding students English language development or Ogilvy-Stuart (2014) which looked to explore the dramatic increase in students from Hong Kong in British boarding school and the level of contribution that curriculum has played in the increase. Criticisms of these are that despite providing more information regarding one of the student demographics at the school focussed in the research, Ogilvy-Stuart's work does not look specifically for English curriculum contribution and Sabawi does not look at curriculum but more the learning of English via the internet and social learning of language.

Blandford's (2004) book looking at English curriculum development in International schools makes a valid point that all staff working in an international school should consider themselves teachers of English. It could be argued that this is particularly true of residential staff in international schools and even more so for British International schools or international schools that teach an English curriculum. This could also be considered true if we were to extend this concept and acknowledge that all residential staff contribute to the curriculum, in that they are a constant contributor to not only any curriculum that is explicitly planned (activities, lessons and the like) but also that which is informally or unintentionally provided.

It should be the aim of every boarding school to develop a residential environment that is an attractive place to live and work, allowing students to broaden their social, cultural and academic horizons (Steel *et al*, 2015). In addition it is often a key objective for parents that their child becomes proficient in English and they are willing to pay in addition to their child's tuition and boarding fees for access to the right programme that supports this. Having highlighted key links between English language, academic success, and opportunity within a residential setting, there is little doubt that the development of provision around English language in a residential context should be explored.

When considering language provision and programmes in a Thai school, the work Rugasken and Harris (2009) was reviewed. Their research conducted a study in which Thai students were exposed to English formally through classroom instruction and through informal field experiences in 2003 and 2005 during residential camps at a Thai school. During the 2005 programme, one English camp leader conducted a study for a three-student group to assess how well the programme assisted in language acquisition through writing. The results indicated the immersion programme was successful not only in language acquisition but also in cultural understanding for all the programme participants and made the claim that residential programmes offer suitable opportunities for development of academic and social language development and one could reasonably argue that this was due to the residential nature of the environment. In the research the further implication of the work identified the need to address how immersion programmes evolve and the correlation between immersion and second language acquisition. A limitation of this study is the sample size which was only three students from a potential sample size of between 120-180.

There are many acronyms associated with programmes and courses designed to enhance English; IEP's (Intensive English Programmes), ELP's (English Language Programmes), HIP (High Intensity Programme) and DLP (Dual Language programme).

Broadly speaking ELP's have the aim of involving and immersing students in an English Environment and are popular among International schools. Merz and Fox (2016), identifies that the development of English Language is fundamental to academic achievement and how parents are keen for the introduction and development of ELP's. These findings are congruent to Breidenstein *et al.*, (2018) who discussed the desires of fee paying parents and the hegemonic perspective of instruction being solely in English. A hegemonic perspective on language involves the categorisation of specific languages or language variations as more or less esteemed (Bettney, 2022). In discussing perspectives on language, Metz (2019) argued that hegemonic attitudes toward language, highlighting instances where Standard English (SE) and Standard American English (SAE) is favoured without question and is almost dominant among educators. Bettney (2022) goes even further to suggest that this overarching approach is evident on a broader scale in international schools, where English is unequivocally positioned as the superior instructional language. Criticisms of Bettany and Metz would include that they focus on singular language environments (where the L1 of all learners is the same) rather than an international school residential environment such as school A which has twelve different first languages who place different values on the predominance of SE and SAE.

Based on a review of the studies of Rifkin (2005), Tarone and Swain (1995) and Moussu (2006), there are several constructive guidelines which would aid the development and implication of any English development programme;

- Second language (L2) acquisition is socially constructed from interactions with others particularly with native speakers.
- Student anxiety learning L2, particularly in an immersive setting may be higher than in a traditional classroom setting but this can be offset when there are many L2 learners such as in a residential setting.
- Understanding learners is key to planning appropriate language instruction including the impact of technology and the evolving expectations of both learners and parents.
- Programmes should be high quality and have relevance to learners. There must be progress for students to be invested and find value. Where there is a gap between learner expectation and reality students may fail to make satisfactory progress.
- Consideration must be given to the cultural expectations and differences of those in the programme. For School A this would need to reflect the desires of parents from different Asian countries with regards to the perceived value of English development as well as the needs and expectations of the students themselves, reviewing higher education pathways and course choices in order to provide relevant and valuable support.

There is little doubt or contrary evidence that suggests the access that students have to residential staff allows an opportunity to offer an enrichment or development programme that would support boarders in English language development (Holden *et al*, 2010). Given the guidelines outlined about programme design, research was carried out to gain better insight into what current provision was available in the day and boarding sectors of School A as well as to what students, staff and parents think this should look like. As always this kind of research must be done in such a way as to promote equality of empowerment and focus on the development of capacities as well as capabilities that in turn support the development of every individual (Kelly, 2009).

Chapter 3 Research Paradigm/Position

When designing a research project, it is essential to consider the "research onion" framework developed by Saunders (2007). Saunders' work breaks down the research process into its distinct layers which include; philosophy, approach, and strategy, and additionally explores how these layers interact and influence each other. Understanding this interplay helps in effectively structuring and planning the research. When considering research philosophy, Schulze and Krauss as cited in Tuli, (2010, 6,(1) pg99) identified that the 'traditional view regards the social sciences as largely similar to the natural sciences, and that researchers who adopt this approach are concerned with discovering laws concerning human behaviour'. A key epistemological debate in social science research centres on whether the methodologies and principles used in natural sciences can be applied to the study of social phenomena (Bryman, 2016). Ultimately, when we consider ontology and epistemology we can think of ontology as asking what exists, and epistemology as asking how we can know about the existence of such a thing.

A fundamental start point for research project design is research philosophy and includes the key concept of 'reflexivity', in which researchers identify and disclose themselves within their research in order to understand their part and influence in it (Cohen, Manion and Morrison, 2013). Positionality is an explicit statement by the researcher reflecting where and how they feel that they have affected their research so that the reader can make a more complete understanding of the truths therein (Holmes, 2016 and Smith *et al.*, 2021). Holmes (2020.8(4), pg.1-10.) later went on to simplify his explanation to 'positionality is normally identified by locating the researcher's position in a relationship to three areas: the topic under investigation; the research participants; and the research design, context and process'. Ultimately, clear research principles assist others in understanding one's research.

Positionality is a vital consideration for researchers and plays a vital role in mediating the outcomes of educational research particularly in how the researcher writes about their findings Bell and Walters (2018). Within academic research, recognising positionality holds significant importance as it enables a researcher to grasp the inherent biases present in their work. Coe *et al* (2021), highlight a criticism of positionality, suggesting that it may place too much emphasis on identities, potentially overstating or exaggerating biases that may not have significantly impacted the research participants. Notable work on positionality by Bryman (2008 and 2016) and later by Clark *et al* (2021) who had Bryman as a coauthor, suggested that while it is important for researchers to acknowledge and identify their positionality in relation to their research, there is little to no practical guidance on

how to manage researcher biases or navigate subjectivity. In contrast to this idea of positionality being the cornerstone of unbiased research, Coe *et al* (2021), Clark *et al* (2021), and Czerniawski (2023) argue that positionality lacks nuance, particularly in its tendency to overlook the intersectionality of identities and experiences. Among these three researchers it was widely accepted that researchers who focus on specific identity markers may fail to consider the complexity of how multiple identities intersect and interact, ultimately shaping individuals' perspectives in more intricate ways.

The work of Czerniawski (2023), presented the opinion that researcher's positionality may also affect their ontological assumptions or what they think they know about a situation or group. One disadvantage of being a part of several groups can mean a researcher is simultaneously an insider and an outsider. One could reasonably presume that there is a potential risk that this may lead to the researcher compensating for being an outsider within some groups. When considering my own research, this may result in me interacting differently with non native and native English speakers. I need to be careful that I don't speak for my research participants who are not native English language speakers, my research needs to reflect their voices (Bourke, 2014). As a native English speaker, I don't have an inherent right to scrutinise the challenges faced by international students. However, in my role as an educator and Housemistress, responsible for supporting international students, I have a professional obligation to explore their issues and perspectives to foster both their pastoral and academic development. This responsibility could introduce bias, as I may inadvertently seek or expect answers shaped by my own views as a native speaker regarding English language development in boarding schools, answers that may not actually exist or be necessary.

Roles	Personal
Teacher. Manager. Colleague. Friend. Housemistress. Employee. Rival School. Researcher.	White. Expatriate. Native English Speaker. 17 Years experience. Middle Class. Worked with international students in the UK. Worked with international students in Thailand.

Table.1. Self identified factors that may affect positionality

In order to better understand my own positionality and experiences which may affect my research I have outlined my roles in Table.1. Within these positions I also become an insider or outsider. For example, I am a teacher and Housemistress in my own school (insider to the school community and experiences of the school) but if I request information from other schools, I am an outsider which may limit the availability and type of information shared with me. The work of Buy *et al* (2022) discusses the impact of being both insider and outsider when conducting research within your own and other education settings. His work suggests that this can create duality and that defining a specific position is more difficult as a result. The researcher is “either viewed as an ‘insider’ belonging to the group of academic colleagues or as an outsider coming from a different academic institution” (Buy *et al*, 2022. 32(13), pp.2034).

As identified in previous research (Sullivan, 2024), as a native English speaker, I am an outsider to the students and parents involved in my research, which may limit the depth of the data I collect. Czerniawski (2023), highlights that the tension between being an insider and outsider can be heightened if schools are partially or fully funding a course that requires research. This raises concerns, such as how to present results that may not reflect positively on the institution providing the funding. While this should not apply to my research, as my findings aim to offer suggestions for enhancing existing programmes, it remains important to consider when interviewing and sharing results with key stakeholders, including parents and school owners. Remembering at all times that ultimately I will be sharing the findings of my research as an employee to my employer about my place of employment and the views of its staff, students and parents.

It must be noted that the way in which one views subjectivity in research is highly dependent upon one's personal experiences and beliefs. Both the work of Bourdieu's (2001) “Science of Science and Reflexivity” and Gingras' (2010) “Sociological Reflexivity in Action” discuss the impact of sociology on research, in the case of Bourdieu particularly his work on the sociology of education. It is widely accepted that reflexivity is about acknowledging your role in the research and how as a researcher, you are part of the research process, and your prior experiences, assumptions and beliefs will influence the research process. This bias is an important ethical consideration for all research, but of particular relevance when the researcher is an insider or where there is potential for possible asymmetrical power like within my own research with students, parents and owners within my own school.

However subjectivity is often presented as a polar opposite to objectivity. In this sense, objectivity is often seen as an absence of bias, thus implicitly implying that subjectivity is equated with bias. Both Bourdieu (2001) and Dean (2021) discuss

reflexivity and subjectivity of researchers in education. However, while the former discusses the vital need to explore positionality in post and its impact on both researcher, participant and action generated from the study, the latter argues from a Bourdieusian perspective about “the pitfalls of reflexivity as a must” (Dean 2021 pg178). Regarding the dangers of being an outsider of the group or minority being explored can lead to the reflexive eye being more of a focus than the results themselves. Dean (2021, pg181) also promotes ‘caution against the over-promotion of reflexivity’ claiming that ‘the reflexive methodological work should be the servant of research findings that aim to highlight inequalities and tackle social injustices, rather than its equal partner – a tool rather than an end in itself’. In order to identify and understand my own positional and reflexivity for my own research it will be beneficial to consider my ‘subjectivity, self-sociological analysis, and researcher-participant relationship in order to prevent feelings of coercion of participants to complete a questionnaire or interviews’ (Marguin *et al*, 2021. Pg19).

Bell (2005) suggests that reliability, validity and generalisability are the essential quality criteria for traditional research. Bell (2005) also identifies when conducting small scale research, particularly within your own research setting it can be more difficult to fulfil generalisability and sometimes reliability, suggesting that qualitative researchers conducting small scale investigations in their own settings may employ a more alternative quality criteria. As generalisability is the concept of a sample being representative and ‘findings being legitimately generalised to a wider population’ (Bryman, 1998. Pg 35), and reliability being the ‘consistency of results or dependency of a measure’ (Clark *et al*. 2021).

Given the nature of interpretivist, qualitative research and the data they generate, the research often finds itself defending against claims of subjectivity. Bassey (1999) suggests that the idea of internal validity, trustworthiness and transferability are a more effective way to look at qualitative, small scale, own setting research like this study. Identifying or anticipating problems at the beginning of the research cycle and explaining how they will be dealt with may improve validity and to consider trustworthiness instead of reliability would help examine the appropriateness of the research methods chosen, as well as how robustly and systematically they have been implemented.

Williams (2016), strives to unpick and reveal the physiological issues hidden within social research and discusses the original work of Saunders (2007) and the concept of the ‘research onion,’ who suggest that when discussing research philosophy, starting with positionality is essential at the start of any research project. This involves

considering the set of beliefs about the nature of reality being studied, or our ontology (what can be known and how we view the world), as well as epistemology (how we can know and how the world should be investigated). Ontology is typically understood through two dominant perspectives: realism and relativism (or nominalism). Burton, Brundett and Jones (2014), Bell and Walters (2018), and Thomas (2022) provide similar definitions of ontology, with a common theme emerging from their explanations. Their work suggests that realism posits that the world exists independently of human perceptions and interpretations. In contrast, nominalism holds the belief that a researcher's understanding of the world is shaped by their inner subjectivity and the 'lens' through which they view it. Our ontology informs our epistemology, determining what knowledge exists and how we will attempt to gather it. Williams (2016) further explains that our epistemological stance typically aligns with either a positivist or interpretivist approach. Some research begins with a broad theory that becomes more focussed as the study progresses (positivist and deductive), while other research starts with specific observations that lead to the development of a hypothesis (interpretivist and inductive).

Several authors on research methods highlight the strong connections between positivist/deductive approaches and quantitative data, as well as between interpretivist/inductive approaches and qualitative data. One key advantage of quantitative data is that it provides a higher degree of control and precision, often delivering clear, definitive results. In contrast, qualitative data can be more subjective and open to interpretation, lacking the same level of objectivity (Thomas, 2022). To address my research question, I will primarily adopt an insider perspective, engaging directly with participants and employing a more qualitative approach. However, it is important to consider the work of Jackson (2011) and a recent paper by English and Nielsen (2023), both of which explore mixed-epistemology research. This approach integrates elements of both interpretivist and positivist paradigms, suggesting that research can benefit from combining these perspectives. My own research will be primarily interpretivist looking at qualitative data, however I may also choose to include relevant information regarding grading scores, entrance tests, value added scores as well as recruitment, retainment figures and financial information which would be quantitative and may result in more of a mixed method approach.

Burton, Brundrett and Jones (2014) explain that positivist researchers aim for researchers to seek generalisation and quantitative data by using a scientific approach. In contrast, interpretive researchers focus on exploring individual perspectives to gain deeper insights into the social world, primarily through qualitative data collection. Understanding the distinctions between these two paradigms and their associated methodological preferences is crucial for recognizing

both their differences and overlaps. Such overlaps in methods often lead to a mixed methodology, which combines both qualitative and quantitative data.

1.1 Research Design

As discussed in previous work (Sullivan, 2024) it was discussed how Punch (2009) impresses that methods should follow from questions. Implying that how we do something should depend on what we're trying to find out. He stresses the influence of research questions on research methods and that this can be a useful teaching/learning tool. This type of empirical data can be qualitative or quantitative and Hammersley (1992: pg41-43) highlighted important similarities. Crotty (1998), suggests it can be a useful tool for the researcher to phrase a research focus into questions to help understand what the best research approach is;

1. Explore the current provision for English Language development available in School A.
2. Evaluate the benefits for stakeholders within a boarding school for developing English language programmes.
3. Determine the barriers and limitations of programme development in a residential setting.

Thomas (2022) emphasises the importance of examining research questions by considering both the researcher's perspective (particularly in relation to subjectivity) and the attitudes of participants or respondents who may be involved or affected by the findings. Additionally, it is prudent to conduct an evaluation of consequences, assessing how one variable may influence another (e.g., x appears to cause y). Neither approach is inherently superior, and the combination of these methods increasingly known as mixed methods research, is becoming increasingly common. Thomas (2022) also considers one of the main advantages to a mixed methodology approach to be that the limitations of one can be offset by the other, for example; conducting a questionnaire may produce large amounts of data which may lack depth, Interviews could then provide more details and depth of a smaller sample of respondents.

Using this approach we can look more critically at questionnaires. Bryman, (2008) identifies that questionnaire offers much flexibility to the researcher when considering method of delivery and volume of data. For example, questionnaires are an efficient tool for collecting a large volume of responses and, consequently, a substantial amount of data. They can also be administered online, facilitating remote access to respondents and promoting anonymity through platforms such as SurveyMonkey or Google Forms. The process of designing and distributing an ethical,

well-constructed questionnaire is thoroughly documented (Crotty, 1998; Bryman, 2008; Punch, 2009; Thomas, 2022) and almost all suggest that key considerations should include question design, sequencing, and the type of questions used, as these will influence the kind of data generated. Crotty (1998), also offers the critique that despite careful planning, however, the response rate may still be low.

The work of Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2013, pg498), is particularly relevant as several important factors in questionnaire design are discussed, with 'four key areas highlighted to guide construction: question content, question wording, response formats, and question sequencing'. Given the number of potential respondents relevant to my research stakeholders, a semi-structured questionnaire could be a suitable approach. This would allow me to gather both numerical data and more detailed qualitative data from open-ended, text-based questions. Closed questions, such as dichotomous and multiple-choice questions, would be employed to generate nominal data that is straightforward to analyse. Since some respondents may be non-native English speakers, this format ensures that responses do not 'discriminate against how articulate respondents are' (Cohen, Manion and Morrison., 2013, p. 476). A common criticism of questionnaires with only closed questions is that they limit respondents from offering additional remarks or providing additional information they feel is relevant to the question. Lambert (2019) argues that this restriction may lead to reduced engagement, encouraging 'mindless' or less thoughtful responses, which could negatively affect the reliability and validity of the data collected.

With this in mind, and considering my goal of understanding the needs and desires of stakeholders, I will also include open-ended questions. This approach aims to keep respondents more engaged and capture valuable or thought-provoking insights that might not emerge through closed questions alone. Such additional information could help shape follow-up interview questions, particularly if patterns arise among stakeholder groups that warrant further exploration. Bryman (2008) highlights the similarities between self-completion questionnaires and interviews, suggesting that questionnaires can effectively inform the development of structured or semi-structured interviews.

The impact of beneficence (potential of research to improve a respondents situation) is an important ethical consideration. Where there is no monetary incentive for respondents, certain groups may be in a position to benefit from any action taken as a result of the findings of the research. Where for students this could be a better programme available and therefore more of a holistic benefit, if the owners (2 of

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whom are also parents of school students) of the school participate in questionnaires (that are not anonymous if conducted by me as an insider researcher), better recruitment and retention of students presents an opportunity for them to make more profit. There is therefore a danger that the responses given may be biased or less genuine in order to develop a profit boosting programme. In order to try and circumvent this, it will be important to consider the types of questions to promote honesty (Sudman and Bradburn, 1982).

Chapter 4 Research Methods -

Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2013, pg498) discuss several considerations for questionnaire design, outlining four essential areas to aid in construction including; 'question content, wording, response forms, and question sequencing'. Given the diversity of potential respondents in my research, a semi-structured questionnaire would be appropriate as this format would allow for the collection of both numerical data and in-depth, open-ended responses. Closed questions, particularly dichotomous and multiple choice answer questions, would be used to generate nominal data that is easy to analyse and given that a number of the respondents may be non native English speakers would not 'discriminate against how articulate respondents are' (Cohen Manion and Morrison, 2013. pg476). However, a common criticism of exclusively closed-question formats is their limitation in allowing respondents to add remarks or relevant information. Lambert (2019) suggests that this can reduce genuine engagement, encouraging "mindless" responses that may lack depth, ultimately affecting the reliability and validity of the collected data.

Considering this and my aim to gain a deeper understanding of stakeholder needs and preferences, I plan to also include open-ended questions in the questionnaire. This approach is intended to keep respondents engaged while also capturing valuable insights that might not emerge through closed questions alone. The additional information gathered could then inform the design of questions for follow-up interviews, especially if patterns arise across stakeholder groups that warrant further exploration. Bryman (2008) recognises the relative similarities between self-completion questionnaires and suggests that they can be used to inform the creation of a questionnaire and structured/semi-structured interview.

In previous research (Sullivan, 2024) I have discussed the work of Cohen, Manion and Morrison (2013. pg475) who identifies open questions as a way to collect a level of 'authenticity, depth of response and honesty' and argues that these are 'hallmarks of valid qualitative data'. This invitation to respondents to provide their opinions is of course not without its limitations, including generating too much detailed data which is then difficult to draw comparisons between respondents or some respondents may opt for the 'don't know' response generating no useful data at all. Krosnick and Presser (2010. pg 267) suggests one way to avoid this abundance of oversharing is to include 'questions that may generate this ambiguous oversharing of information in a pilot questionnaire, sent to a sample which may aid the researcher in reducing and refining the questions or inform some of the closed answer questions'. I should

therefore consider sharing my pilot questionnaire with people not involved in my study to see how questions are interpreted.

Braun *et al* (2021) emphasise the value of using both closed and open-ended questions to gather a diverse range of data. In this study, the questions will aim to assess stakeholders' understanding of students' English proficiency levels and how they perceive the support provided by boarding to foster development in this area. Additionally, it will be important to include questions that elicit feedback on the current level of provision, alongside open-ended prompts to identify any further support or resources that EAL (English as an Additional Language) boarders and other stakeholders may feel are necessary (Bell, 2005).

While researchers generally agree that well-crafted questions can offer both a “wide-angle lens” for broad insights and the potential for rich, focussed data, Thomas (2022) suggests that response rates are typically higher for interviews than for questionnaires, as participants often feel more comfortable sharing information in a face-to-face or virtual setting. He also notes that in-person interviews allow for observation of physical cues and behaviours, which are valuable for building rapport and encouraging honest, detailed responses—benefits that may be less pronounced in phone interviews and absent in questionnaire formats.

One of the limitations for my questionnaire was that I chose to include a neutral option. Most questions ranged from ‘Strongly Agree’ to ‘Strongly Disagree’ on a 5 point likert scale with the middle option being ‘Neither Agree or Disagree’. In the results this created almost a data void of between 17%-40%. questionnaires without absence of a middle or ‘neutral’ option in rating scales tends to increase the magnitude of ratings by a small amount (Krosnick and Presser, 2010). However, it is worth considering that removing the neutral option, particularly with student responses could lead to some students selecting answers that don’t truly reflect their feelings. One key criticism (Grieg, Taylor and Mackey, 2007) of including neutral options, particularly with children, is that it ultimately reduces ambiguity as neutral options can sometimes mask respondents' true feelings, either due to indecision or lack of engagement and so it could be concluded that removing it can encourage participants to make a more thoughtful choice, providing more actionable data.

My findings were generally concurrent to this suggestion. While the students' response rate was high (73.5% of 126 students), the response rate from parents was very low (25.9% of 120 families). Despite translating the questionnaire into four languages the predominant responding nationality was Thai. One reason for this is

that parents were provided with a QR code to access the form during students' collection and drop off times. Even though the QR was sent to all parents, I think the face to face request during collections encouraged more parents to complete the form and the vast majority of these parents are Thai. The school also uses Google Education Suite to communicate with parents, which can also be problematic for the mainland Chinese parents to access without a VPN. If the study was to be repeated in the future, researching a more accessible survey platform is something I believe would be beneficial to the range of data collected. It is worth noting that responses from staff eligible to participate in the research (no staff from the early years campus were included as these students are not old enough to be boarders) the response rate was 51% from mostly (76%) British expatriate teaching staff meaning some key demographics represented in the boarding community did not have a member of staff from the same cultural background complete the survey. This would have provided a more in depth view across the cultural identities in the community and potentially less bias.

Some of the most useful data collected in terms of depth and relevance was from the interviews. This abundance of data was useful and provided good insight into the views of teaching staff across the key areas of the school, however the amount of qualitative data was vast and it took a huge amount of time to accurately transcribe the interviews in order to analyse and identify patterns or commonalities within the responses. The easiest way to do this was by breaking down the interview by questions and then summarising key points and an example of these summaries can be found in Appendix 6. If the research was to be continued in the future I believe it would be useful to extend the interviews to a sample of parents, allowing for more personable face to face collection of data, with a translator to allow for first language communication which would make parents feel more at ease and hopefully yield greater depth and variety of answers. Consideration should be given as to whether this would be applicable to online meetings so parents would not have to travel or be in the country which again would increase data collected and ultimately, triangulation of data collected from stakeholders.

Triangulation is a method used to increase the credibility and validity of findings by combining multiple data sources, methods, theories, or perspectives (Thomas, 2022). The goal of triangulation is to cross-verify information and interpretations which should, in turn, make the research conclusions more reliable and reduce the likelihood of bias.

Using different research methods helps to avoid risking a lack of strong triangulation. For my research, data (both qualitative and quantitative) was collected from different sources that included; development plans, questionnaires and interviews with stakeholders. The different sources offered strong data triangulation, however as previously mentioned, low response rates will have reduced this slightly. Combining different research methods, (collecting both qualitative and quantitative data) promoted strong methodological triangulation where statistics support qualitative finding and vice versa. Given that the study was only conducted by myself as the sole researcher, the level of 'investigator triangulation' was low. If the research was repeated, involving multiple researchers to collect or interpret data would help to reduce individual bias.

External validation could have been sought by seeking scrutiny from other relevant audiences. In the case of my research this could be other boarding practitioners from other schools both international and in the UK (peer validation). Given the qualitative methods used to collect the data it will be important to remember that a researcher can never completely remove the human element and as such I think that in order to generate meaningful and insightful data there needs to be a compromise between validity and reliability.

Chapter 5 Research findings

Based on the work of Bassey (1999. Pg70) who suggests that 'data should be condensed into meaningful statements and subsequently supported by appropriate evidence' and Ezzy's (2002. Pg93) advice I processed the data and noted the key themes (thematic coding). In order to present the findings I will endeavour to provide a summary of key findings from each of the sample groups; students, staff and parents before drawing on the main similarities and differences across the groups in order to address the key research questions I am addressing;

1. Explore the current provision for English Language development available in School A.
2. Evaluate the benefits for stakeholders within a boarding school for developing English language programmes.
3. Determine the barriers and limitations of programme development in a residential setting.

1.1 Summary of key findings from Students

The response rate from students was 73.5% of 126 students which I considered a high level of response. There was a good spread of responses across the various age groups and nationalities in the community with the highest number of responses from the four largest demographics (Thai 60%, Chinese 15.2%, Burmese 9.1 % and Korean 7.2%). There are actually more Korean boarders than there are Burmese so this indicates a lower response rate from this nationality.

Data revealed 87.9% of the students have English as an additional language with 43.5% having previously had or were currently receiving extra EAL support in the day school, suggesting that around half of the students would be categorised as having low or very low level English. 59.2% of students either agreed or strongly agreed that 'boarding offers good opportunities to practise and use English in both academic and social contexts Student perceptions of identifying reasons that their parents chose a British international boarding school (question 12, student survey) 47 students identified that developing English skills was a key factor, with the second and third highest identified factor being developing English related to academic and English for post 16 study. I was surprised that the holistic reasons for attending a boarding school were as low as only 4 or 5 students identifying perceived attendance linked to improving independence or the extra opportunity available. These results were slightly contrary to the 45% of parents who cited developing self management skills and boarding activities programmes as reasons for choosing the school.

Despite identifying the importance of English in current and future academic success, students also identified that laziness or lack of motivation was a barrier to them developing English within the boarding setting which was most common as a response in the KS3 (Year 7-9), this was less common in the KS4 (Y10-11) groupings and potentially reflects that the importance of good English skills during examination courses increases the intrinsic value of developing good English skills.

When asked if students feel that there are any challenges or barriers within the boarding environment that hinder the effective support of English language development a significant 79.6% of students said there were no barriers. Of the 20.4% (as identified across Years 7-13) who said there were barriers to developing English in the boarding environment, friendship groups speaking in first language was the most common response. 36.3% of students identified barriers as being 'low or extremely lacking in confidence' when joining the boarding community, 52% of whom identified that they have 'noticed changes in my confidence or ability to communicate effectively in English since joining boarding'.

Students also identified several areas that could be developed in order to better support English language development in boarding, a summary of which can be found in Appendix 5. These included (but were not limited to) fun/games/group activities in English (16 students), extra academic enrichment English support (11 students) and regular structured sessions for English development (10 students). Key stage 4 and 5 (Y10-13) students also identified mentoring from older students as a suggestion for developing support.

1.2 Summary of key findings from Parents

The number of parents' responses was very low, with only 25.9% of 120 families completing the questionnaire (a summary of key questions found in Appendix 4). As previously mentioned this may be due to a lack of accessibility for Chinese parents unable to access google forms in China, but the lack of engagement from parents across all nationalities was disappointing given that the form had been translated into Chinese, Thai and Korean. From the responses gathered 84.8% were from Thai families, which, although is representative of the largest demographic of boarders may have presented some bias as the respondents vastly outnumbered the other nationalities not proportionally represented in the boarding community, in and 5 other people (15.2%) from 4 nationalities responded including Chinese and Korean parents.

93.9% of respondents have English as an additional language and 75.8% consider themselves not confident English speakers. This may be reflected in the reasons parents identified for choosing an English boarding school for their child where the English speaking policy was identified by 87.9% of parents and English speaking staff 84.8% of parents. Developing self management skills (45.5%) and the boarding activity programme (45.5%) were also identified by parents, but this is a higher percentage than students perceived reasons, suggesting that parents understand and value the extra programmes more than students and the potential value these programmes have when linked to language development.

63.6% of respondents felt that 'boarding offers sufficient opportunities for children to practise and use English in both academic and social contexts', however, where just over half the respondents (51.5%) felt that boarding 'provides children with enough support and resources to enhance their English language skills' this also suggests that 48.5% of respondents neither agreed or disagreed with this statement which suggests a lack of knowledge about what boarding provision there is for EAL students. This level of neutrality was also seen in response to being asked if the 'day school effectively addresses the individual needs and proficiency levels of students in English language development' (54.5%) and also when asked if 'boarding effectively addresses the individual needs and proficiency levels of students in English language development'. The most positive response was to question 9 'noticed improvements in their child's English language skills since they started boarding' where 84.8% of respondents agreed or strongly agreed.

When given the opportunity to state 'what additional resources, programmes or support could the school provide to further enhance your child's English language development?', almost all the answers included a reference to 'English programme development', 'English for academic study' or 'academic English for university'. This feedback may be due to the nature of the questionnaire which explains that it is exploring parent perceptions of the EAL provision within boarding or 'title bias'. This type of bias occurs when the wording or context provided by the title influences how respondents interpret and answer the questions. In discussing 'title bias' Krosnick and Presser, (2010) identify the possibility that 'Title bias' can lead participants to form expectations about the questionnaire's purpose or sway them toward particular answers, thereby impacting the objectivity and reliability of the data collected, which would explain the bias in answers to question 17. Again the level of neutral responses suggests that if the research was to be repeated that removing the neutral option would have provided more focussed data, as the neutral responses ranged from 9.1% to 54.4%, responses which could have given more clarity to the data on

certain questions. Overall responses from parents suggest that parents are happy with the current provision (there were no disagree or strongly disagrees to questions about current provision), however, they also offer ideas for further development of provision particularly surrounding 'academic English' or 'English for university', which is similar to suggestions made by students in their survey responses.

1.3 Summary of key findings from Staff

Data from staff was collected in the first instance by questionnaire and then by semi structured interviews with those staff who were happy to be further involved in the research. In total 33 responses were gathered from the questionnaire with a further 7 semi-structured interviews conducted, with a sample across the four key stages in boarding and a variety of subjects. As previously mentioned, responses from staff eligible to participate in the research (no staff from the early years campus were included as these students are not old enough to be boarders) the response rate was 51% from mostly (76%) British expatriate teaching staff meaning some key demographics represented in the boarding community did not have a member of staff from the same cultural background complete the survey.

Data collected indicated that 91.2% of staff consider boarding 'offers sufficient opportunities for children to practise and use English in both academic and social contexts', subsequent questions reveal that 38.3% disagreed that boarding 'provides boarders with enough support and resources to enhance their English language skills', the follow up question asking respondents to justify their answer provides clarity where staff identified the issue of some first language friendship groups limited opportunities to speak English but also included comments identifying opportunities for language to be developed in a social context but not academic context and that staffing numbers of boarding staff may be a reason for this. Not having staff dedicated to more formal English development in the evenings or prep time.

Staff were asked questions relating to students' English assessment requirements to join the school and also questions to gauge understanding of the EAL provision within the day school and 'graduation requirement for these students to join mainstream lessons. There was significant lack of understanding in these areas, highlighting that 73.5% of staff have not seen the school entrance exam, 76.5% of staff do not know the entrance criteria for students with English as an additional language and 67.6% of staff not knowing what is required for students to 'graduate' from the intensive EAL programme. The wider impact of this is that staff are not aware of what level of English students should have and would not be planning for this in lessons. In answer

to question 17; ‘I think that the day school effectively addresses the individual needs and proficiency levels of students in English language development?’, there was a close split between staff who felt individual needs of EAL learners are met (47.1%) and staff who did not (52.9%). This split was similar to question 21 which looked at whether staff felt ‘boarding effectively addresses the individual needs and proficiency levels of students in English language development?’ Where 51.5% of responses were neutral and 42.5% agreed or strongly agreed. Justifications given for these 2 questions can be compared in Table 1 below.

Day School responses to meeting individual needs of EAL students	Boarding meeting responses to individual needs of EAL students
<p>Positive justifications: EAL classes see progress. Well staffed EAL department. Use of the ‘Bell’ method to measure proficiency in Reading, Writing, Listening and Speaking. The EAL programme is better for low ability students than well scaffolded mainstream lessons. Good cultural integration within extra-curricular activities, trips and events.</p>	<p>Positive justifications: Mixing nationalities in rooms and house groups. Buddies for new students. Extra one to one session for identified EAL students. Less pressured environment to practise speaking. Support from friends to try.</p>
<p>Neutral justifications: Not all staff fully understand the structure of the EAL curriculum. Primary students benefit less from separate EAL classes. Hard to gauge ‘for each individual student’. Too many variables to give an accurate answer (class size, teacher, subject, students motivation). Good support for KS2 and KS3 but falls short of effective support for academic purposes in KS4 and KS5.</p>	<p>Neutral justifications: 14 of 17 neutral staff identified they do not know what measures are taken in boarding to support individuals in EAL development. English speaking policy is hard to enforce in the ‘home’ environment. Safety and comfort in large own nationality groups.</p>
<p>Negative justifications:</p>	<p>Negative justifications:</p>

<p>Lack of staff training. Class teachers are 'ill equipped' for very low ability language learners. Support is limited for literacy based subjects. Lack of understanding of EAL curriculum and assessment criteria. A big void is created for students in EAL intensive that rejoin mainstream in terms of curriculum content and specific terminology.</p>	<p>There is an 'own culture divide' which doesn't promote English speaking. English policy is not consistently enforced by staff. Demographic of cohort meant not all bedrooms are mixed nationalities Better collaboration between day and boarding is needed. Lack of time, resources, training and staff to offer a robust support system to very low ability EAL students.</p>
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Table 2. Summary of key points regarding staff perception of individual support for EAL students in both Day and Boarding environments.

Despite staff identifying in previous questions that boarding provides a less pressured environment that can support social development of English language, 78.85% of staff felt there were significant barriers to boarding supporting the development of English. Most frequently identified barriers included boarding staff not speaking to students in English, lack of staffing, lack of first language English speakers in the houses and own culture preferences. When asked what additional provisions the school could provide, there were 36 suggestions that fell into the categories of; professional development for staff, activities, resources, curriculum or policy.

Details from the questionnaires were used to inform the semi structured interviews. A summary of the transcribed interview responses can be found in Appendix 6. Commonalities between the responses from the interviews include identifying gaps between Intensive EAL English and subject language that create a void in the knowledge and limit progress when EAL intensive students rejoin mainstream lessons. Staff interviewed understood that as a 'for profit' school there are financial benefits for accepting low ability English learners but at present the provision in both day and boarding is not enough to adequately support these students. Staff also highlighted concerns about a lack of multiculturalism amongst students who tend to gravitate towards friends of the same cultural background which creates a barrier to the development of English language. This includes the boarding environment where it was felt that staff did not know enough about the specific provision in order to make an accurate assessment, but this was linked to a lack of staff to dedicate to specific programmes.

Analysis of the data collected showed that students, parents and teachers all identified that developing English language is a lead contributing factor for enrollment at the school, however perceived barriers to the success of this varied. Where parents and staff identified external factors such as staffing and time dedicated to English development, students identified a lack of motivation as a key factor. Students showed that they understood the value of developing English but also that they would be reluctant to attend additional support programmes. Students identified that they would be more likely to attend additional support if this was run by day school staff. One potential justification for this could be a lack of native English speaking staff within boarding and therefore students would not see this as impactful role modelling of the language. Both parents and staff identified a gap 'post EAL intensive' and students, parents and staff highlighted a desire for academic English support (aimed at GCSE and A-level) in order to address provision to support sufficient academic progress.

Results highlighted a lack of understanding from parents and staff regarding what boarding currently offers which suggests that the current provision is not structured or advertised enough which may detract from the value that students identify from boarding provision. All three stakeholder groups identified that boarding is a good environment to develop English language, with students and parents identifying improvement in confidence and ability during their time in residence. This was reiterated by staff but with the added implication of boarding being more suitable for the development of social rather than academic English.

The current provision for English Language development available in School A includes a two tier EAL support programme (EAL or EAL Intensive). Admissions testing includes a cognitive ability test (CAT4), as well as a New Group Reading Test (NGRT) for students with a native English speaking background or 'Oxford' for students who have English as an additional language. The Oxford Test of English for Schools (OTES) is 100% online and computer adaptive. One of the key benefits to the OTES is that it assesses students' ability to understand and communicate effectively in Speaking, Listening, Reading and Writing at three CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference) levels: A2, B1 and B2. This then provides that start point for either EAL or Intensive EAL support and ultimately provides EAL staff with the framework for what to teach as the curriculum of 'Cambridge Prepare' promotes progress for students to sit KET (Key English Test) or PET (Preliminary English Test) and attain a CEFR level. This is to enable students who go on to require IELTS certification for higher educational study an accurate transition from one grading system to another without gaps in ability. Intensive EAL students are only accepted

up to Year 9 and students must be able to demonstrate a level of English proficiency appropriate to accessing GCSE curriculum when joining or progressing into Year 10.

However, there is not currently a specific level required to graduate the intensive EAL programme and students are assessed on a case by case basis. This may be a contributing factor for issues identified by staff between English proficiency and a lack of academic English as the standards are not consistent across all students. Students are also grouped based on age rather than English ability, so there are often students of the same age in widely mixed ability groups which may further contribute to progress or lack of, experienced by children in the intensive EAL groups. Joyce and McMillian (2010) identify there are advantages to mixed ability classes including peer support and the potential rapid development for low proficiency students this is in contrast to much research (Murphey and Arao, 2001; Dai and Rinn, 2008 and Brown, 2009) who suggest that homogeneous 'streaming' (or 'setting') not only provide better quality learner-learner interactions, it is found to be less stressful for low proficiency learners and therefore reduces chances of becoming demotivated as a result of inferiority complex. There are also the added benefits for staff, allowing for more appropriate task design and differentiated instruction which would directly address issues raised by staff in this research.

Obong (1997) stressed the importance of meeting the academic and non academic needs of learners in the context of academic performance, particularly in multi-cultural environments. Despite the fact that Obong's research focussed solely on University students, this is also relevant to the boarding school environment and parallels can be made between this claim and the vast majority of the 'ethos' or 'visions' as advertised on boarding school websites. School A promotes several statements that directly reflect this intention including;

'Our boarding programme offers our students the chance to succeed beyond the classroom'

'...providing them with the supportive working environment that they need in order to achieve...'

'...opportunity to work to the best of their ability by offering them further support, encouragement and individual care and wellbeing outside of school hours'

(Statement from School A's website 2024).

However, when taken altogether the data presented here provides evidence that EAL students' needs are not being met in full. There is evidence to suggest that a formal boarding programme supporting language development would benefit students, in

both a social and academic context, particularly if this was structured in conjunction with more appropriately streamed classes and clearer, more consistent assessment in the day school. This would address the lack of understanding about what is done to support English language development in boarding while at the same time increasing the quality and quantity of dedicated EAL teaching. This would be a programme which would incur additional costs to the parents (potentially replacing the current programme and intensive EAL charge).

Motivation of students, programme design and staffing are identified as key barriers to the success of current provision with parallels being identified by both students and staff. It could be suggested that a dedicated residential programme may generate extra income for the school, which could be reinvested into additional staffing and staff training in order to improve the curriculum which the work of Huang *et al* (2011), (although not focussing directly on English language development) identifies as key contributing factors towards student engagement and motivation. There is potential for a strong correlation between this research and numerous studies that look at higher education outcomes and satisfaction based on integration and how these contribute to academic success.

Chapter 6 Ethical considerations

The British Educational Research Association (BERA) Guidelines are a set of ethical principles and best practices intended to guide researchers in the field of educational research. These guidelines are designed to promote high standards of integrity, professionalism, and responsibility, ensuring that research is conducted ethically and respectfully. A copy of the completed and signed university ethics form can be found in Appendix 1.

I identified several ethical considerations that will need to be addressed in order to comply with BERA guidelines in order to make sure that the research is non-exploitative. Providing participants with detailed information of the research purpose and what exactly they will participate in as well as information regarding right to withdrawal, reading their transcripts and also providing information regarding what happens to their information afterward will greatly increase participant safety and consent (Coe, *et al.* 2021).

Using online surveys which do not identify respondents was a useful tool to promote anonymity and to allow for this key information to be translated into participants' own language so it is fully understood and easily sent along with the questionnaires. For interviews, it was empirical that participants were made to feel safe, non threatened and their contributions important, allowing them to read back their transcript and make any amendments, were all important in the promotion of good ethics and hopefully minimised consent withdrawals and promoted respect for participants. I had hoped to create an environment where all participants and respondents felt valued and happy to contribute to the research and the compliance with BERA ethics guidelines played a vital role in this and ultimately the success of the research overall.

At all times responses to google forms were anonymous and results only shared in summary form so that individuals were not identifiable. For all areas of data collection, respondents were given detailed information on the purpose of the research for high levels of transparency and integrity. The method of collection, storage of data and right to withdrawal were explained to respondents in order to promote effective and robust data protection and privacy. The BERA Guidelines are widely regarded as a benchmark for ethical practice in educational research, promoting responsible, socially conscious research and encouraging professional

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competence. Compiling with these guidelines helped ensure that as a researcher, I upheld high standards of expertise, integrity, and ethical responsibility throughout my research process.

Chapter 7 Limitations

Several areas of the research went well. This included the results from the interviews with staff which were valuable in part because of the honesty of respondents but also the variety of staff who agreed to take part across the range of relevant key stages and subjects. Also, the responses from students which were a good sample size and many of the points raised in the results became useful when designing the semi-structured interviews. Outside of the formality of the research questionnaire, students were interested in the topic and several of them mentioned in informal discussions that they were grateful that they were surveyed and felt it contributed to their student voice. A number of students were also keen to learn more about the research and dissertation process in general and by working and conducting the research at the same time it provided older students with a first hand view of the process. It is my personal belief that it is a fantastic opportunity to role model a wide variety of skills as well as share the difficulties with academic study when you live with students and that it is good for them to see adults engaging in professional development and academic study in order to show that learning and self development doesn't end with school or university.

There were a number of things that I considered problematic during my research. Firstly the time constraint of the hand in date being a tight turn around from the submission of module 3. There were several staffing issues at school which meant that my proposed time frame to conduct interviews and subsequently write the bulk of this report was not possible, working full time in both the day school and the boarding house impacted greatly on the time I was able to protect in order to dedicate to research and writing when combined with the other responsibilities of my roles. Within the research itself, the responses in the sample were not truly reflective of the demographic of staff, students or parents. Responses to the staff and parent questionnaires in particular, were limited in terms of nationalities. The responses to the parent surveys were very low in number which was disappointing given that the surveys were sent out in 4 languages. This meant there was limited insight into parent values and desires. Lack of strong triangulation across 'boarding schools' meaning that the reliability of the results may be reduced. There were a number of questions across the parent and students questionnaires where removing the neutral response option from questionnaires would help improve the impact of this data and something I would strongly suggest for future research.

Things that I believe contributed to the success of my research include my knowledge of the provision both within the day and boarding sectors of the school. Importantly, the staff who were interviewed were very honest when sharing their views, opinions and experiences and I believe this is due to my positive relationships with staff as well as feeling confident that their anonymity would be protected and also understanding the relevance of the research to their respective roles in the school. Overall my attitude to the research is positive. I found the subject to be interesting and relevant across both day and boarding school. I felt confident in my ability to conduct the interviews, making staff feel at ease and asking non scripted follow up questions which generated very useful data. On reflection I regret not allocating time to conduct interviews with a sample of parents and staff as I feel this would have generated a great amount of relevant and useful data.

Key takeaways for me as the researcher include better understanding that teachers, parents and students all understand that English is a vital requirement for current and future academic achievement and progression which ultimately affects employability and future earnings. Many students understand the intrinsic value of the English language but lack strong intrinsic motivation to develop at a faster pace or deeper level. Striving to help students develop English language is done in a delicate balance with helping students to maintain their cultural identities which is vital to boarders mental health and the feeling they are part of a community. Enforcing English speaking policies to promote English is a necessary but difficult job, particularly in a multicultural house and the difficulty results in a lack of consistency in its application. The effort to create a 'home from home' environment that is only English speaking is almost impossible with very low level ESL students and is something which can only be addressed by entrance criteria or support, both of these issues at School A are not currently optimal for student support or integration.

Several findings of this research warrant further discussion and research. Programme development is an area where there is undoubtedly scope and justification to develop a fully immersive programme for very low English speakers. However this would need to align with a reform of the existing way that 'intensive' EAL and EAL support is delivered. This would include employing additional specialist EAL staff and more rigorous testing during the course to find the appropriate graduation point. Another area is how to address the deficit in current mainstream lesson content and EAL 'graduation' ability which was highlighted across KS2 and KS3 with several staff identifying the knock on effect this deficit has when students begin GCSE learning in KS4. Reviewing the setting and streaming approaches for Intensive EAL lessons to enable more effective and efficient teaching by narrowing the range of pupil

attainment in a class. In some development contexts the approach 'Teaching at the Right Level' (TaRL) has become popular, which has some crossover with setting or streaming. The outcomes of these studies tend to be higher than the overall average and is something to be considered when reviewing how age and current proficiency affect the organisation of groups.

Actions that have been taken as a result of the findings from this research include the EAL provision at School A, in both the day and boarding sectors, is under review to see how improvements can be made. This included the boarding induction process which included the information sent to parents and students, the allocation of 'buddies' and the language portion of the entrance exam. The Sixth Form boarding students now have access to tuition from the British Council to study the IELTS preparation course which was something highlighted by parents and students that would immediately improve the provision. Cost-Benefit analysis for an immersive English language programme is also planned. Looking at including specialist, residential ESL staff leading a curriculum for very low language students which have lessons in the day school and also replaces part of the evening activities to include evening lessons in boarding. This may ultimately replace the 'intensive' EAL programme and such a programme would be offered at an additional cost to parents which would potentially increase boarder numbers, academic outcomes for EAL students and ultimately generate more revenue for the school.

Chapter 8 Conclusions and recommendations

One limitation of the literature review was that much of the available literature on residential programmes and the success of EAL programmes has been conducted on University students. Almost no research has specifically been conducted in boarding schools so it was difficult finding research from which to draw the most accurate comparisons. Expanding the sample used in the research to include other boarding schools would have produced a greater set of results, whilst also improving triangulation further.

Despite this, the research has provided a detailed exploration of the current provision for English Language development available in School A. This was met with an outline and discussion of the entry requirements and current EAL programmes. It was also evaluated by staff, students and parents in the questionnaire and subsequent staff interviews. Shortfalls in the current boarding provision were identified as; staff numbers and training, the impact of large, low ability same nationality groups and this was in conjunction with issues in the current day school EAL assessment and curriculum. Suggestions include specialist evening lessons for residential students and the potential for a separate, immersive language programme as a replacement or parallel to the current day school provision have also been made, which would provide short term and longer term resolution for the issues identified. When evaluating the benefits for stakeholders within a boarding school for developing English language programmes, this was partially met.

When considering the potential for future research, it would be prudent to assess the direct impact of how better provision would benefit EAL learners and staff which could be done with follow up surveys or a case study which could provide in depth results, if only for a smaller sample of students. Including interviews with students would provide further evidence of the impact on students' motivation and mental health. When determining the barriers and limitations of programme development in a residential setting, this has been partially met. Further discussion with a wider sample of stakeholders that could include owners and other members of the senior leadership team may provide other limitations and barriers not discussed in this research. It is also a recommendation that further research should include questionnaires without absence of a middle or 'neutral' option in rating scales in order to increase the magnitude of ratings. Including interviews with a sample of students and parents in order to generate more detailed responses would provide

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greater insight and potentially provide greater guidance of what additional programmes should look like. Finally, conducting research with a larger sample, potentially including schools in the UK, many of whom rely on international students to bolster boarding numbers and also face challenges when accessing an English curriculum, as this would help improve triangulation and validity of the findings.

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Appendices Additional materials used in the research.

Appendix 1 - Completed Ethics form

For this module ethical considerations are a vital component and an ethics release form must be completed, reviewed by your University supervisor, signed off by them and uploaded before any research can be submitted for the final dissertation. Please upload to Moodle separately

Any educational project that involves research is likely to raise ethical issues, especially as people and children are likely to be directly involved.

ETHICAL CONSIDERATIONS.

Identify any ethical issues that may arise and how you intend to deal with them. If you are conducting any research that involves children you will need to gain formal consent/permission from the school and parents and also prove that children will not be harmed or in any danger (physical or psychological). Once approved, you must include this ethics release form as an appendix to your dissertation.

Name	Nicola Sullivan	Supervisor	Peter Williams
Course Taken	MA in Residential Education		
Working Title	'To what extent can EAL provision within boarding schools be further developed to better support its stakeholders?'		

Confirm you have read the BERA guidance?	YES
Project aim Briefly state the aim and objectives of your research project	Research as to whether there is room for reformation and expansion of existing EAL provision programmes offered by boarding schools to students that could offer potential benefit across several areas of the school ultimately increasing recruitment, retainment and academic achievement.
Outline your educational context and how you intend to carry out your research e.g. I work in a secondary school as a Maths teacher and plan to carry out research in my own school	I work in a fee paying international school in Thailand as a Housemistress. I plan to carry out research in my own school as well as reaching out to conduct research with staff both at other international fee paying school and also fee paying schools in the UK.
How do you intend to pick your sample?	All boarders and boarding parents will be invited to complete the questionnaire with a return rate from students of around 80% and from parents around 40% which will give a representative sample. Interviews will be conducted with people identified as key stakeholders and volunteers from the wider staffing body.
Confirm you have emailed this to your supervisor as well as uploaded it to Moodle?	YES
Confirm your proposal compliant with GDPR regulations? (Came in to force 25 th May 2018)	YES

Name: Nicola Sullivan

Student Number: 2124594

Supervisor Name: Peter Williams

Post-Graduate Ethics Release Form 2023

THE UNIVERSITY OF
BUCKINGHAM
FACULTY OF EDUCATION

For this module ethical considerations are a vital component and an ethics release form must be completed, reviewed by your University supervisor, signed off by them and uploaded before any research can be submitted for the final dissertation. Please upload to Moodle separately

	Ye s	No	N/A	Explain how you are dealing with these (must be completed if yes)
Participant well-being				
Does your proposed research involve the participation of human beings? Tick all that apply	X			<input type="checkbox"/> Early years/pre-school <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Ages 5-11 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Ages 12-16 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Ages 17-18 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Adults <input type="checkbox"/> Unknown – specify below <input type="checkbox"/> No participants
Will the project involve working with or studying minors ("under 16 years of age)? If yes, how will signed parental consent be obtained?	X			Written consent obtained from parents as part of the terms and conditions of joining the school.
Have the participants been informed about the project aims, processes and any possible risks involved?	X			For questionnaires, participant information will be provided. Interviews in English with a translator if required and a written information sheet.
Is it possible that participants might experience unease, concern, anxiety or embarrassment during your research? How will this be minimized?	X			Anxiety by being interviewed face to face. Informed consent, right to withdraw. Create a safe, neutral space to conduct interviews.
Can the participants withdraw at any time without harm or risk of prejudice and have they been informed of the option to do so?	X			This will be explained to them at the beginning and they will be reminded of their right to withdrawal after each interview.
Are there any power issues regarding the relationships involved in the research?	X			Me to students who I live with Owners to Me
Will any participant's position or treatment be prejudiced in any way if they choose not to participate?		X		
Have you considered the ethical implications of selecting data and the obligation to represent participants' views accurately?	X			Anonymity in questionnaires, recording of interviews to allow for accurate transcription.
How are you ensuring no individual can be identified?	X			Name changes in write up., Participant number allocation, GDPR, anonymous online questionnaires.
Research methods				
Will your research involve interviews/surveys/questionnaires to participants?	X			Interviews and Questionnaires
Will your participants be able to opt out of questions?	X			All questions will be non compulsory, explained to participants at the beginning of each interaction.
Are there any questions that could be considered offensive or inappropriate?		X		
Does your research involve accessing confidential information? If yes how have you sought permission to do so and have you followed correct protocols?	X			Overviews of test scores and assessment information obtained through school access.
Are there any intellectual property issues regarding documents or resources you wish to use?		X		

Name: Nicola Sullivan

Student Number: 2124594

Supervisor Name: Peter Williams

Post-Graduate Ethics Release Form 2023 THE UNIVERSITY OF BUCKINGHAM
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For this module ethical considerations are a vital component and an ethics release form must be completed, reviewed by your University supervisor, signed off by them and uploaded before any research can be submitted for the final dissertation. Please upload to Moodle separately

Have you made clear to participants who owns data that you collect?	X		This is on the consent form and participant information.
How have you ensured that data you collect about participants will be kept safely and securely?	X		Any Hard Copies - Locked cabinet in private locked office, Soft Copies - Secure school system in encrypted file.
What data protection issues have you anticipated and have you familiarised yourself with relevant strategies for storing of electronic data? See the Data Protection Act for storage of personal information on personal computers.			Ensure encryption and anti-virus software where possible. results stored on a secure, password protected school system not a personal computer. We are a google school and they provide the following statement: Here is Google privacy notice which Google has clarified that they're in compliance with European Privacy Standards and GDPR. For your question, about DPA (data protection agreement) in place with Google as the data controller. There is no contract or agreement signed documentally. As customers, we can only accept their data processing agreement shown on our school Google Workspace admin console. For details of data processing agreement, please view this page .
Impact of research			
Have you considered what impact your research may have on participants and what change it may bring about in them?	X		Changes to the relationship of researcher and stakeholders. Change to activities, and academic achievement via improved provision.
Is there a need to debrief participants after the project?		X	
Have you obtained written permission from your Head or the Employer of any school/workplace you are working within?	X		From; Head of Boarding, Head of Secondary and Head of Primary
Has your employer given you written permission for any research to be carried out in the place you work?	X		(This must also be included in the appendices of the dissertation) From Headmaster and CEO, Heads of Boarding, Secondary and Primary.
Ethical approval from other bodies			
What, if any, ethical approval/permission is required from other bodies? See BERA guidelines and core book: Cohen, L., Manion, L. & Morrison, K. (2011) <i>Research Methods in Education</i>		X	None
General			
Are there any ethical issues/questions that have arisen for which you may have difficulty managing and need more support. If yes please detail here.		X	

I confirm that to the best of my knowledge:

Name: Nicola Sullivan

Student Number: 2124594

Supervisor Name: Peter Williams

Post-Graduate Ethics Release Form 2023 THE UNIVERSITY OF
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For this module ethical considerations are a vital component and an ethics release form must be completed, reviewed by your University supervisor, signed off by them and uploaded before any research can be submitted for the final dissertation. Please upload to Moodle separately
The above information is correct and this is a full description of the ethics issues that may arise in the course of this project

Student Name: Nicola Sullivan *NSullivan*
Date: 14/5/2024

Supervisor's declaration	I agree that this form has been reviewed and I believe it to be an accurate ethical assessment made by this student	Name: Peter Williams
		Signed: <i>Peter Williams</i>
		Date: 24.5.24.
Feedback Comments		

Appendix 2 - Preliminary SWOT analysis of boarding in School A by senior boarding staff.

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Inspection was EDT Gold, boarding policies and procedures were very good. ● Variety of things currently on offer ● English native language speakers. ● Lead staff are experienced. ● Price compared to competitors ● Location (rural but within 45 mins of the airport and Bangkok) ● Non-Selective ● Recent Refurbishment ● Y4-Y13 ● Learner Profiles applicable in boarding ● Widest variety of nationalities to date ● AD with day staff and access to library ● Saturday sessions offered ● Varied Trips and activities program. ● Highly qualified and experienced staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Despite an English speaking policy in communal areas, students tended to speak only in L1. ● Staffing levels (impacting on variety of activities and staff morale). ● Acceptance of 'low calibre' students creating their own culture groups. ● Facilities downstairs ● Some facilities are outdated ● Culturally risk averse ● Workloads and staff burnout ● Student Voice ● Language testing on entry ● Communication of EAL/Day/Boarding ● Structure of AD ● Wider EAL Provision and development ● Marketing ● Utilisation of staff on duty rota
Opportunity	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Employment of UK Graduate students. ● Still have spaces to fill and increase numbers. ● The promise of renovation. ● Dynamic environment where there is a safety for staff to try new things that enrich boarder experience. ● Creating of a boarding USP ● Positive word of mouth ● Competitors are expensive ● Utilisation and development of current staff ● Curriculum growth ● EDT ISQM inspections (going from silver to gold) ● SIP focus (3.1,3.3 2022-26) ● Addition of EAL HoD 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Finance - Far reaching across facilities, staffing, programmes available and the need to get 'bums on seats'. ● Relationship of day school staff with boarding - Many new staff do not have experience in a boarding environment. ● Location from the city. ● Competitiveness ● Economic pressure on parents ● Lack of travel for international boarders ● Limited international recruitment opportunities. ● Reduction in boarding staff numbers ● Big name Competitors ● Culturally Risk Averse ● Politics of school ownership and management.

Appendix 3 - Preliminary SWOT analysis of EAL provision within boarding at School A

Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Students live in an immersive environment ● Mix of cultures and nationalities ● TEFL qualified staff live onsite ● AD time allocated ● Staff on site ● Students tested on entry ● Reading program has had good results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Motivation ● AD times not focussed on EAL development ● Extra tuition only for BDST ● Lack of staff/space with current AD set up ● Doesn't cater for wide ability range ● No industry standard testing on entry (KET/PET) ● Staff training ● Student intrinsic engagement
Opportunity	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Restructure of AD ● Marketing ● New students have joined ● Potential USP for boarding ● Only Thai school to offer a tailored, residential program for EAL (extra year, extra fees, foundations) ● Online Learning ● Extra Fees/chargeable ● Direct impact on classroom learning ● Online Learning ● English regarded as important for next academic steps and employment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● COVID-19 ● Buy in from staff parents and students ● Economy and finance ● Culturally risk averse ● Staff Turnover (residential staff/day staff/SLT) ● Devices ● Parents' dedication to international schooling.

Appendix 4 - Results from question 6 from the parent questionnaire

6. Which of the following are factors that motivated you to select a British International boarding school for your child (please tick all...
 33 responses

8. How do you feel about the following statement: 'Boarding provides my child with enough support and resources to enhance their...
 33 responses

12. How do you feel about the following statement: 'I think that the day school effectively addresses the individual needs and p...
 33 responses

Name: Nicola Sullivan

Student Number: 2124594

Supervisor Name: Peter Williams

14. How do you feel about the following statement: 'I think that boarding effectively addresses the individual needs and proficiency level...적인 요구와 능숙도 수준을 효과적으로 해결한다고 생각합니까?

33 responses

- Strongly Agree เห็นด้วยอย่างยิ่ง 非常同意
전적으로 동의함
- Agree เห็นด้วย 同意 동의함
- Neither agree or disagree ไม่แน่ใจ 既不
同意也不反对 동의하지도 반대하지도 않
음
- Disagree ไม่เห็นด้วย 不同意 동의하지 않
음
- Strongly Disagree ไม่เห็นด้วยอย่างยิ่ง 非
常不同意 전적으로 반대

Name: Nicola Sullivan

Student Number: 2124594

Supervisor Name: Peter Williams

Appendix 5 - A table summarising extended answer questions from the student survey.

Q12 Students perceptions of why their parents chose a British international boarding School	Q14 Challenges or barriers to developing English in Boarding	Q15 What else can be done?
English Skills - 47	Low level students find it very hard when they start common feedback from Thai Y7-9	Fun/games in English - 9
English related to academics/curriculum - 12	English is hard, need to be brave to communicate Thai Y7-9	Regular English sessions of english development - 10
English related to onward study - 21	Friends speaking their own language identified across 4 language groups from 7-13.	Extra/AE English Support - 11
Independence - 4	Amount of vocab (most frequent Thai Y7-9)	Encourage english speaking in activities - 2 Group activities in English - 7
Expensive in own country - 1	Self identified laziness/motivation (All nationalities (Y7-9 most common) More highlighted amongst non thai.	More English staff in boarding - 2
Family already at the school - 3	Confidence - those who identified as joining with a low level of English and Chinese students (Y7-11)	Mentoring from older students - 4
Boarding facilities - 3		Time allocated for students to practise English - 7
Extra opportunities - 5		Absolute English Policy - 1
Reputation of the school - 5		Display vocab around boarding - 1
Pressure in Chinese Education System - 3	Boarding is a safe environment to try things on your own and boost your confidence.	Story Time - 6
Western Culture influence - 1		Reading time/book club - 3
Lack of faith in Thai schooling - 5		Better Role modelling from staff - 7
		writing competitions - 1
		More resources to help English - 4
		English movies 3

Appendix 6 - Summary of interview transcripts for staff interviews.

	Interview 1	Interview 2	Interview 3	Interview 4	Interview 5	Interview 7	Interview 8
Q1 - What is your nationality?	British	The interviewee is from Ireland.	British	British Canadian, with a British father and Canadian mother.	British.	British	British
Q2 - What is your first language?	English	English	English	English	English	English	English
Q3 - What is/are your role/s within BIST?	Head of 6th Form	English as an additional language teacher and a Y8 tutor.	Head of English	Secondary EAL teacher and Head of the Best House, Edwards.	Head of Inclusion for the whole school, which includes the English as an Additional Language (EAL) department.	Housemaster of Winter House (the boy's house) and a language support teacher focusing on primary years 3 to 6.	The interviewee is a Year 6 class teacher, teaching and learning lead in primary, and assistant head of primary.
Q4 - Can you give reasons that you think parents chose a boarding place for their children?	Reasons include the school's reputation, accreditation, size, facilities, and the overall feel that their child will be cared for and supported socially and academically. The British element may be less important than the reputation, facilities, and word of mouth. English being the language of	Possible reasons include opportunities for children, positive personal experiences, family problems or concerns, and inability to manage at home.	Reasons include geographical location, inability to care for children due to work commitments, providing a similar education they had, sending children to a British or international school, and geopolitical concerns.	Some reasons mentioned are: parents have busy lives and want someone to take care of their children, wanting their child to be socialised, being influenced by promotional materials, and being able to afford it.	The interviewee suggests reasons such as convenience, travel time, and the boarding experience of full immersion in the school culture.	Parents choose boarding for nurturing morals, behaviour, and etiquette, as they may not have the time or energy to do so themselves due to work.	The interviewee believes that many parents choose Bromsgrove for their children to receive a British education system and for the independence that boarding encourages. Boarders tend to be more independent, organized, and responsible.

	instruction is more important than the British curriculum.						
Q5 - Do you think that boarding currently offers a good environment for students who have English as a second language to develop their English abilities?	Yes, the boarding environment provides many opportunities for EAL students to practise English in different contexts and settings, though enforcing English as the common language can be challenging due to students reverting to their native languages.	Yes, the interviewee thinks boarding offers a good environment for EAL students to progress quicker in English due to increased exposure and usage.	Yes, boarding provides a space for collaborative work, routine, and a safe learning environment with adult support. However, the lines can be blurred regarding expectations for students to speak English all the time.	Yes, it's a good environment, but it would be better with more diverse nationalities forcing students to speak English to communicate.	The interviewee believes that while there are opportunities for English practice in boarding, the predominantly Thai student body can be a barrier as students tend to default to their native language.	Yes, because the common language in boarding is English, there are student mentors, tutors, and staff communicating in English, ensuring students speak English most of the time.	Yes, the interviewee believes that boarding provides an immersive environment where EAL students are constantly exposed to and encouraged to speak English, leading to rapid growth in their English skills and confidence.
Q6 - Do you feel that there are any challenges or barriers within the boarding school environment that hinder the effective support of students' English language development?	The challenge is finding a balance between allowing students to use their first language for understanding and encouraging English practice. It's difficult to have a one-size-fits-all policy.	Potential challenges include student well-being issues like homesickness, students sticking together in language groups, and the tendency to switch off from speaking English during downtime.	Challenges include the temptation to speak in their native language with roommates or peers who share the same first language, and being surrounded by people who speak the same language.	Social dynamics, temperament, and personality play a huge role. Outgoing students may do well, while shy students may struggle.	The interviewee cites the tendency of students from the same nationality or ethnicity to gravitate towards each other and speak their native language as a challenge, making it difficult to strike a balance between comfort and English language development.	Yes, new students with very low English proficiency tend to revert to their first language, influencing others and creating an exclusive environment. Finding the right balance between practicing the first language and developing the second language is challenging.	The interviewee suggests that homesickness can be a barrier, as some students may revert to speaking their native language when missing home, hindering their English language development.

<p>Q7 - Do you currently have very low level EAL students in your lessons?</p>	<p>In a year 8 math class, there are some students with low English levels who tend to revert to their home language for support.</p>	<p>The interviewee has provided informal support in the past, such as working with mentors and tutors to help low-level EAL students understand questions and command words.</p>	<p>Yes, there are a couple of students in a year 10 second language class whose English ability is significantly lower than others.</p>	<p>Currently no, but previously in year 7 with very low English ability levels.</p>	<p>Yes, the interviewee has observed very low-level EAL students, mostly in secondary classes.</p>	<p>Yes, some students joined last term with very little English, but their progress has been phenomenal as they are motivated and engaged in learning English.</p>	<p>Yes, the interviewee currently has three students in EAL intensive and four students who have recently returned to the classroom from EAL intensive, totaling seven students with EAL needs.</p>
<p>Q8 - Can you give some examples of how this has impacted both positively and negatively on your lessons (planning, delivery, resources, class cohesion).</p>	<p>Having low-level EAL students presents challenges in terms of time spent ensuring they understand instructions and tasks, which can slow down progress for the whole class.</p>	<p>In small EAL classes with varying levels, there can be multiple lessons happening simultaneously, hindering group work, class cohesion, and lesson flow due to disruptions and differing paces. A specific example is where mid term joiners are put in the same class, creating 3 different classes of different levels of learners in the same class which had a big impact on planning, delivery and progression of learners.</p>	<p>In terms of planning, the interviewee has lower expectations for the writing of lower-level English learners and provides them with strict grammatical guidelines, while more able students can use varied criteria.</p>	<p>For low-level students, the focus is on encouragement, basic drilling, and finding ways to engage them based on their interests.</p>	<p>Positively, it can encourage teachers to slow down the pace and include more students. Negatively, teachers may tend to focus on the higher-level students, leaving lower-level students behind. The interviewee believes there is variation, with more adaptation in primary levels and less in secondary due to curriculum content pressure and the need to cover material quickly.</p>	<p>Positively, it inspires the teacher to plan and differentiate lessons for new students to access the curriculum. Negatively, it can be challenging when students join mid-year, and it must be unsettling for the children themselves.</p>	<p>The interviewee explains that having EAL students requires more differentiation and planning, which can be time-consuming but also encourages teachers to think creatively. It can also impact lesson flow and delivery, as teachers may need to teach multiple lessons within one to accommodate different language levels.</p>

<p>Q9 - Do you think the current level of provision for EAL students at BIST supports sufficient academic progress?</p>	<p>It's difficult for the interviewee to comment on EAL progress in Key Stage 3, where most EAL students are.</p>	<p>Yes, the interviewee believes the small classes, focused learning, and adaptability support EAL students in making quick progress before transitioning to mainstream classes.</p>	<p>Switching exam boards from Cambridge to Oxford has helped as the Oxford papers are more accessible for EAL students. However, concerns include removing EAL students from certain subjects like science in Key Stage 3, and the limited subject options available, particularly at A-level and BTEC.</p>	<p>It depends on the year group. Y9 into 10 is highlighted as an important transition that often some students are not ready for,</p>	<p>The interviewee thinks the provision generally supports good progress for EAL learners but suggests identifying and better supporting those who don't make as much progress and stay in the EAL program longer. The interviewee also emphasises the importance of teaching tier two vocabulary.</p>	<p>It's a mixed opinion - the curriculum book provides everyday language, but students miss out on English lessons when withdrawn for EAL support, hindering their progress. More in-class support could be beneficial.</p>	<p>No, the interviewee believes that the current EAL provision in primary is not effective, as students are taken out of English lessons for EAL intensive but then struggle to catch up when returned to their regular classes due to the significant gap in levels.</p>
<p>Q10 - Do you think that boarding's current provision and support to develop EAL students abilities is sufficient?</p>	<p>Boarding provides a lot of support, such as preparing students for English proficiency tests and personalised curriculum. There's an emphasis on ensuring students have the necessary English level for university.</p>	<p>The interviewee is unsure about the specific EAL provision in boarding but believes the staff cares about supporting students holistically.</p>	<p>The interviewee is unsure about the specific provisions in boarding but believes that more staffing attention and home communication may be provided for students who need more support.</p>	<p>It seems good based on the interviewee's limited perspective, with a positive vibe and some good new hires</p>	<p>The interviewee believes there is a good emphasis on English in boarding but suggests more English-focused events, activities, and strategies to encourage reluctant English speakers to practise the language.</p>	<p>From a boarding perspective, they are doing all they can, but there is room for improvement, such as dedicated English learning time, reading comprehension, or novel study sessions.</p>	<p>The interviewee believes that boarding's current provision and support for EAL students seem to be working well, based on the progress observed in boarders with EAL needs.</p>

<p>Q11 - Do you think that the immersive experience that boarding provides for EAL students an effective way to develop English skills?</p>	<p>The immersive boarding environment, where students are surrounded by English 24/7, is highly effective for developing English skills. However, long holidays can disrupt the momentum.</p>	<p>A fully English immersive environment could be effective but may overwhelm students with very low English levels, so a balance is needed to ensure their well-being and ability to communicate.</p>	<p>Yes, the immersive experience helps develop relationships and bonds with peers and teachers, which can support social development.</p>	<p>It depends on the student's social dynamics and personality.</p>	<p>The interviewee believes the immersive experience is an additional opportunity, particularly during quieter times when students must interact with others outside their language group, but it needs to be supported and balanced with outlets for students to use their native language.</p>	<p>Yes, definitely. Being surrounded by English every day in school and boarding provides an effective immersive environment for developing English skills.</p>	<p>Yes, the interviewee believes that the immersive boarding experience is the best way for EAL students to develop their English skills, as they are constantly exposed to and encouraged to use English, unlike day students who may revert to their native languages at home.</p>
<p>Q12 - What do you think the impact (both positive and negative) of accepting more students with a lower level of English would be?</p>	<p>Accepting more low-level EAL students could be positive for business and providing opportunities, but it presents challenges in terms of segregation, accessibility of activities, and differentiating instruction for varying levels.</p>	<p>Positives include increased revenue, potentially leading to more EAL provision. Negatives include fewer mainstream students, potentially lower GCSE grades, and a harder sell for the school.</p>	<p>Positively, it could be a marketing opportunity to showcase progress made by low-level English students. Negatively, there needs to be more training for EAL teachers, and teachers in other faculties are not held accountable for providing appropriate resources and teaching for low-level</p>	<p>Negatively, it may impact the school's ability to market itself and send students to top universities. There would undoubtedly be some positives, as people can contribute in different ways.</p>	<p>The interviewee believes it could positively encourage more adaptive teaching but negatively impact other learners if not properly resourced with additional staff support.</p>	<p>Positively, it promotes inclusivity and acknowledges that low English proficiency does not equate to low academic ability. Negatively, it can lead to students reverting to their first languages, excluding others and impacting the learning environment.</p>	<p>The positive impact would be increased acceptance and inclusivity among students. The negative impact would be a significant burden on teachers, as the current EAL provision is not adequate, and more collaboration and support from EAL specialists would be needed.</p>

			English learners.				
Q13 - Can you give any suggestions as to how boarding can improve or develop their provision and support of EAL students?	Suggestions include mixing students by language ability, utilising peer support from long-term students, focusing on everyday English beyond academics, and providing clear purpose for activities to practise English in practical contexts.	Suggestions include staff training, shared learning and good practices, involving older students in peer learning, and potentially implementing a separate language program.	Suggestions include providing specialised language teachers for one-on-one or small group tuition, utilising older students as mentors, and incorporating language-focused games and activities.	Suggestions include having a mentor system where older students are responsible for helping younger students progress, and finding ways to motivate and engage students despite distractions like phones and devices.	Suggestions include more boarding activities, language workshops, events open to day students, and strategies to encourage reluctant English speakers to practise the language.	Suggestions include having day school EAL teachers offer afternoon/evening sessions focusing on writing and speaking skills, implementing a reading program like Accelerated Reader to promote a love of reading and improve English proficiency, and having a boarding library for students to access books daily.	The interviewee suggests that boarding should share their EAL support strategies with the day school staff to ensure a consistent approach across all settings.
Q14 - Can you give any suggestions as to how the day school can improve or develop their provision and support of EAL students?	Suggestions include increasing staff awareness of graduation points and English level requirements, understanding what happens when students don't make expected progress, and clarifying policies and expectations for EAL support in the classroom.	The suggestions are similar, with the potential for better links and blended provision between boarding and day school.	Suggestions include allowing more timetabled hours for English lessons, considering entering EAL students for the English as a Second Language exam in Year 10 while continuing to work on first language and literature, and providing more training and accountability for teachers.	Suggestions include mandatory class participation and engagement activities, such as presentations, reading drills, and practising conversational phrases. Building these skills should be integrated across all subjects.	Suggestions include making adaptive teaching for EAL learners a focus in teacher appraisal processes, emphasising tier two vocabulary, using more visual aids, and celebrating students who make efforts to practise English.	Suggestions include having EAL teachers involved in classroom planning and curriculum decisions, as they know the students well, and improving communication between EAL teachers and class teachers.	CPD stuff. The interviewee suggests hiring experienced EAL teachers who can collaborate with classroom teachers to plan and provide resources for supporting EAL students across all subjects.

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Q15 - Considering the focus of this research is to explore 'to what extent can EAL provision within boarding schools be further developed to better support its stakeholders?', are there any further comments you would like to provide?	Further suggestions include giving students ownership and responsibility for practising English during extracurricular activities, and having a clear message that activities are not just for fun but also for developing English in practical contexts.	Further suggestions include staff training by experienced and qualified individuals, structured personalised learning plans with achievable goals, regular student assessments, and effective communication between teachers, parents, and students to address any issues or lack of progress.	The interviewee suggests a culture shift by introducing regular guest speakers and role models to inspire students to value English development, implementing rewards for completing oracy tasks, and ensuring consistent enforcement of the English-only policy across all staff levels.	The interviewee emphasises the importance of focusing on the little things and building positive habits, like greeting others, presenting in class, and developing self-confidence. There is a moral obligation to be positive about the future, especially around young people. Having a good batch of motivated students can make a big difference.	The interviewee suggests increasing the language mix in boarding by accepting more students from diverse nationalities and celebrating role models who push themselves to practise English, as it can translate to academic success.	Implementing a reading program like Accelerated Reader would greatly enhance students' ability to improve their English proficiency by promoting a love of reading.	The interviewee emphasises the importance of involving parents in understanding and supporting their child's EAL provision, as well as providing training for boarding staff, who may have limited experience working with EAL students. The interviewee also suggests increased collaboration and sharing of strategies between boarding and day school staff to ensure a consistent approach for EAL students.
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